

An Overview of Crimean Congo Hemorrhagic Fever

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Introduction

Crimean Congo Haemorrhagic Fever (CCHF) is a zoonotic viral disease that is asymptomatic in infected animals, but a serious threat to the health of humans caused by the CCHF virus (CCHFv). Crimean Congo Haemorrhagic Fever virus belongs to the family *Bunyaviridae*, Genus *Nairovirus*. It is widespread throughout the world and is most common among tick-borne viral diseases. Ticks of the genus *Hyalomma* are transmission agents of the CCHF virus (CCHFV) in humans. The virus is maintained in tick species through horizontal and vertical transmission and spreads to domestic animals, which further carry the disease to humans.

The disease was first reported in Crimea in 1944, it was given the name Crimean hemorrhagic fever. The same disease was identified in the Congo region in 1969, giving rise to its current name: 'Crimean-Congo hemorrhagic fever.' Previous research has found that the disease is widespread around the world, including Africa, Asia, central and southern Europe, eastern Europe, particularly in the former Soviet Union, the Mediterranean, northwestern China, the Middle East, and the Indian subcontinent.

Geographic Distribution

CCHF is currently endemic throughout Africa, the Balkans, the Middle East, and Asia, in nations south of the 50th parallel north. The World Health Organization classifies CCHFv as a high priority pathogen due to the widespread nature of the vector, high fatality rate, and lack of medical countermeasures for illness treatment/prevention.

In 2019, the online database of the Program for Monitoring Emerging Diseases (ProMed) revealed well over 100 recorded human cases of CCHFv across countries such as Pakistan, Uganda, South Africa, Iran, India, Namibia, and Russia, among others in Africa/Middle East/Asia. Spread of CCHFv from endemic areas has been of growing concern for many reasons, especially considering it is already the most widespread tick-borne disease. This spread can be attributed to human movement, vertebrate host migration, and climate change. Its spread can be related to human travel, vertebrate host migration, and climatic change. The Ministry of Health, Iraq, reported 299 confirmed cases and 55 deaths nationwide by CCHF since the beginning of the year 2022. Similarly, Afghan health officials indicate increased Crimean-Congo hemorrhagic fever (CCHF) activity, with 131 new cases reported from July to August 2022.

Crimean-Congo haemorrhagic fever virus in animals

The hosts of the CCHF virus include a wide range of wild and domestic animals such as cattle, sheep and goats. Many birds are resistant to infection, but ostriches are susceptible and may show a high prevalence of infection in endemic areas, where they have been at the origin of human cases. For example, a former outbreak occurred at an ostrich abattoir in South Africa. There is no apparent disease in these animals.

Animals become infected by the bite of infected ticks and the virus remains in their bloodstream for about one week after infection, allowing the tick-animal-tick cycle to continue when another tick bites. Although a number of tick genera are capable of becoming infected with CCHF virus, ticks of the genus *Hyalomma* are the principal vector.

Vector

Many genera of ixodid ticks act as vector and reservoir for CCHF virus. The genus *Hyalomma* are predominantly vital to the ecology of this virus. The incidence of CCHF closely approximates the better-known world distribution of *Hyalomma spp.* ticks. Exposure to ticks represents a major risk factor for contracting a disease. Viral isolations from ticks have been made from two species in the family *Argasidae* (soft ticks) and seven genera of the family *Ixodidae* (hard ticks). At least 28 species of the *Ixodid* ticks distributed among seven spp. genera, (*Hyalomma*, *Rhipicephalus*, *Boophilus*, *Dermacentor*, *Amblyomma*, *Haemaphysalis*, and *Ixodes*) are naturally infected with CCHF virus worldwide.

Transmission

Transmission can be from person to person, through contact with infectious body fluids of the infected person and contact with animal blood or products.

Vertical transmission

Tick vectors aid in the reproduction of the virus presents inside their bodily tissues as they metamorphose from larva to adult. The virus is then transmitted to eggs and adult females by adult females and adult males, respectively. The virus replicates in the tick's midgut lining before spreading to other bodily tissues such as reproductive organs and salivary glands. As a result of transovarial transmission, thousands of contaminated eggs are produced, enough to sustain a huge population of infected ticks.

Horizontal transmission

During the summer and spring months (June-October), the spread of CCHFV between ticks and animals is greater because larvae and nymphs mature into adult form by feeding on blood. When an infected tick bites its host, which is small vertebrate, the virus is transmitted from the tick to the host, where it is then replicated in host tissue and circulated in the bloodstream by healthy ticks feeding on the same host.

Non-viremic transmission

This is another type of viral transmission that does not require an animal to be viremic, but directly transfer from the infected to healthy ticks feeding together. During co-feeding, viral substances present in the saliva of ticks accelerate the viral transmission.

Transmission to birds

Birds are commonly resistant to becoming viremic. No specific antibodies are detected in 37 different species of birds infected with the virus, as CCHFV do not rely on birds as a host for its replication.

Transmission to humans

Humans are considered as the CCHFV's definitive hosts. CCHFV infection is most prevalent in rural places where ticks are abundant, and people become infected after being bitten by infected ticks. Within 7-10 days of the disease, physical contact with infected bodily fluids or blood can transmit the virus from person to person. Contact with infected animal blood can also lead to transmission. In butcher shops, this kind of transmission is quite prevalent.

Symptoms in Human

The incubation period following contact with infected blood or tissues is usually five to six days (depends on the mode of transmission in fact infection via blood or tissue quicker), with a documented maximum of 13 days. The pre-haemorrhagic phase usually initiates with fever, myalgia, dizziness and vomiting and ends on average after 3 days. The haemorrhagic phase is characterized by bleeding from

gastro-intestinal system, urinary and respiratory tract and also skin bleeding ranging from petechiae to ecchymosis. While the clinical spectrum of the disease varies from mild to moderate or severe infection, some cases result in death.

Prevention and Control

The "Global Vector Control Response (GVCR) 2017–2030" was approved by the World Health Assembly in 2017. It provides strategic guidance to countries and development partners for urgent strengthening of vector control as a fundamental approach to preventing disease and responding to outbreaks. To achieve this a re-alignment of vector control programs is required, supported by increased technical capacity, improved infrastructure, strengthened monitoring and surveillance systems, and greater community mobilization. Ultimately, this will support the implementation of a comprehensive approach to vector control that will enable the achievement of disease-specific national and global goals and contribute to achievement of the Sustainable Development Goals and Universal Health Coverage.

Public Health Advice Should Focus on Several Aspects

A. Reducing the risk of tick-to-human transmission

- Wear protective clothing (long sleeves, long trousers)
- Wear light coloured clothing to allow easy detection of ticks on the clothes
- Use approved acaricides (chemicals intended to kill ticks) on clothing
- Use approved repellent on the skin and clothing
- Regularly examine clothing and skin for ticks; if found, remove them safely
- Seek to eliminate or control tick infestations on animals or in stables and barns
- Avoid areas where ticks are abundant and seasons when they are most active

B. Reducing the risk of animal-to-human transmission

- Wear gloves and other protective clothing while handling animals or their tissues in endemic areas, notably during slaughtering, butchering and culling procedures in slaughterhouses or at home
- Quarantine animals before they enter slaughterhouses or routinely treat animals with pesticides two weeks prior to slaughter

C. Reducing the risk of human-to-human transmission in the community

- Avoid close physical contact with CCHF-infected people
- Wear gloves and protective equipment when taking care of ill people

- Wash hands regularly after caring for or visiting ill people

Conclusion

Prevention is the only way to prevent this widespread infection. The disease has more severe impacts in developing countries because of a lack of resources. It is necessary to strengthen prevention measures in order to avoid the spread of the disease to new locations. By taking decisive action, the livestock and health sectors can help to reduce the spread of this disease across the country. Awareness campaigns about risk factors and control strategies can help to educate the public about the risks of this virus.

References

- Aslam, S., Latif, M. S., Daud, M., Rahman, Z. U., Tabassum, B., Riaz, M. S., ... & Husnain, T. (2016). Crimean-Congo hemorrhagic fever: Risk factors and control measures for the infection abatement. *Biomedical reports*, 4(1), 15-20.
- Karakecili, F., Çıkman, A., Aydın, M., Binay, U. D., Kesik, O. A., & Özçiçek, F. (2019). Evaluation of epidemiological, clinical, and laboratory characteristics and mortality rate of patients with Crimean-Congo hemorrhagic fever in the northeast region of Turkey.
- Mourya, D. T., Yadav, P. D., Shete, A. M., Sathe, P. S., Sarkale, P. C., Pattnaik, B., ... & Katoch, V. M. (2015). Cross-sectional serosurvey of Crimean-Congo hemorrhagic fever virus IgG in livestock, India, 2013–2014. *Emerging infectious diseases*, 21(10), 1837.
- <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/crimean-congo-haemorrhagic-fever>

